

Synthesis and characterization of nanostructured thin films of Fe-doped titanium dioxide prepared by polymeric precursor method

Mehrnaz Gharagozlou

Department of Nanotechnology and Nanomaterials, Institute for Color Science and Technology,
P.O. Box 16765-654, Tehran, Iran

E-mail : gharagozlou@icrc.ac.ir Fax : 98-21-22947537

Manuscript received online 25 August 2013, revised 21 May 2014, accepted 22 May 2014

Abstract : This paper describes the development of nanostructured thin films of TiO₂ and Fe-doped TiO₂ with different Fe content on the glass substrate by the polymeric precursor method and spin coating. The prepared thin films were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and atomic force microscopy (AFM). The analysis of the films showed that the adopted method could be used to synthesize pure anatase phase. Also, sizes of Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles decreased when the Fe³⁺ content increased from 0 to 3.0 mol%. The absorption edge of TiO₂ thin films shifted towards longer wavelengths and the band gap energy of TiO₂ thin films decreased from 3.21 to 2.95 eV when the Fe-doped concentration increased from 0 to 3.0 mol%. The average roughness and grain sizes of films were also calculated. The results of photocatalytic test were also showed that the samples with higher anatase phase with little iron concentration have better photocatalytic activity (0.3 mol% of iron).

Keywords : Thin films, Fe-doped TiO₂, polymeric precursor method, band gap energy, photocatalytic activity.

Introduction

TiO₂ thin films deposited on conducting glass are used in novel type solar cells, liquid and solid dye-sensitized photo electro-chemical solar cells, as well as in solar cells very thin organic or inorganic absorbers. Lately, these films are intensively used in diverse attractive applications such as photo-catalysis, photo-oxidation of water, and electro-chromic devices¹.

A number of methods^{2,3} have been employed to prepare TiO₂ films, including electron beam evaporation, sputtering, chemical vapor deposition and sol-gel process. The sol-gel conventional method uses the hydrolytic route, which involves the initial hydrolysis of the alkoxide precursor followed by continual condensations between the hydrolyzed particles forming the gel. Although studies have been performed on the preparation methods of TiO₂ films, there is a lack of information about the preparation of nanostructured thin films of Fe-doped titanium oxide by polymeric precursor method.

The polymeric precursor method was developed by Pechini⁴, being a soft chemical method used to synthesize polycationic powders. This method consists of the

formation of a polymeric resin between metallic acid chelates and a polyhydroxide alcohol by polyesterification in which the cations are uniformly distributed on an atomic level. The polymeric precursor method leads to a more precise stoichiometry besides particle size and morphology control⁵. This method has received a lot of attention due to its simplicity, low cost, homogeneous mixing at molecular level, good stoichiometric control, low processing temperature and the use of an aqueous based processing system. Gouveia *et al.*⁶ and Lessing⁷ provided a description and discussion of such synthesis method.

TiO₂ is one of the most investigated materials for photocatalytic application and usually for enhancement of photocatalytic activity; the nanopowders of this compound with a high surface area were prepared⁸⁻¹¹. There are two main restrictions that decrease the photocatalytic activity of titanium dioxide : a high bandgap of TiO₂ and a fast recombination of the electron and the hole in the TiO₂ structure¹⁰. One of the useful strategies to overcome these limitations is doping of iron in TiO₂ structure¹²⁻¹⁴. The introduction of transition metal ions can result in the formation of a doping energy level between

the conduction and valence bands of TiO₂ and shift the band gap of TiO₂ into the visible region. With the addition of Fe into TiO₂ structure, some new energy bands below the conduction band of TiO₂ were created, which resulted in red shift of TiO₂ absorption edge. With red shift of absorption edge, light absorption of TiO₂ compound is enhanced¹³. At low concentration, iron can trap the electron and the hole generated by light and therefore increase the recombination time of the electron and the hole¹⁴. However, at high concentration, iron ions can act as a recombination centre of the electron and the hole, which results in reduction of photocatalytic efficiency¹¹.

The main methods of produce TiO₂ nanocrystalline thin films are by thermal hydrolysis¹⁵, chemical and physical vapor deposition methods¹⁶, spin coating and dip coating¹⁷. There are large differences in the properties of TiO₂ thin films produced by each technique¹⁸.

In this research, synthesis and characterization of properties of Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films prepared by the polymeric precursor method and spin coating on a glass substrate have been studied using X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and atomic force microscopy (AFM).

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade, supplied by Merck Chemicals, and were used without further purification.

Preparation :

In a typical reaction, the aqueous solution of titanium tetraisopropoxide and iron nitrate (with desired stoichiometry) was added to citric acid solution. After complete dissolution and homogenisation, EG with same amount of citric acid was added to the solution to poly-condensate the citrate complexes with EG as a diol. The solution was heated at 90 °C for 24 h. The viscose polyester solution was dried and heat treated at 450 °C for 2 h to obtain the nanopowder samples. For the preparation of thin films, the prepared viscous polyester solution was deposited on the glass substrates by the spin-coating technique, with an initial rotation speed of 1000 rpm for 10 s, followed by 5000 rpm for 40 s. The thin films were heat-treated at 450 °C for 2 h, to form the nanometric film.

Before deposition, the substrates (2.5 × 2.5 cm, sodalime glass) were cleaned in diluted H₂SO₄ and absolute ethanol for 15 min using an ultrasonic bath. Then, they were thoroughly rinsed with deionised water.

Characterization :

The crystalline phases of the samples were investigated the X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique using a Philips PNA-analytical diffractometer operating with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) as the X-ray source. The topography, grain size and the surface roughness of the Fe-doped and undoped TiO₂ thin films were examined by atom force microscope (DualScope™ DS 95-50) in contact mode with a 10 nm radius silicon tip. XPS was employed to study the surface atomic composition and chemical state of the thin films. XPS data were obtained using a hemispherical analyser with an Al K α X-ray source (hm ¼ 1486.6 eV) operating at high vacuum (P, 107 Pa). All binding energy values were determined by calibration and fixing the C(1 s) line to 285 eV.

The optical properties of Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films were investigated by UV-Vis absorption spectra (Lambda EQ-OC1 spectrometer).

Evaluation of photocatalytic activity :

The photocatalytic activity of films for the oxidation of methyl orange was tested under visible light irradiation using a 500 W halogen lamp. The thin films were placed in beakers, immersed in 20 ml of an aqueous solution of methyl orange (2.5 mg/L). The beakers were placed in a photoreactor at 25 °C and illuminated by a 500 W halogen lamp. The photocatalytic oxidation of methyl orange was monitored by taking UV-Vis measurements after 5 h light exposure.

Results and discussion

Thin films characterization :

The XRD patterns of Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles with different doping amounts of Fe (0, 0.05, 0.3, 1.0 and 3.0 mol%) calcined at 400 °C are illustrated in Fig. 1. Due to the small thickness of thin films and impossible to identify the phases correctly, the XRD analyses were done in powders obtained in the same procedure used to produce the films.

It can be seen that undoped TiO₂ is a mixture of anatase and rutile phases. The diffraction peaks of Fe-doped

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of (a) TiO₂, (b) 0.05% Fe-doped TiO₂, (c) 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂, (d) 1.0% Fe-doped TiO₂ and (e) 3.0% Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles.

TiO₂ nanoparticles with different doping amounts of Fe (0.05, 0.3, 1.0 and 3.0 mol%) demonstrate anatase as the sole nanocrystalline phase and the rutile phase disappears. These results reveal that the doping Fe³⁺ controls the crystalline conversion of TiO₂ from rutile to anatase phase. It must be noted that the presence of the Fe₂O₃ phase can not be observed in the studied range of doping amount of Fe. One of the probable reasons may be the homogeneous dispersion of Fe³⁺ in the TiO₂ lattice because of the similar ion radii of Fe³⁺ (0.64 Å) and Ti⁴⁺ (0.68 Å) and all the Fe³⁺ ions may be inserted into the crystal structure of TiO₂ particles and occupy some of the titanium lattice sites. Another is that the amount of doped Fe³⁺ is so low, which is in accordance with the results of reported in Refs.^{19–21}. In the XRD patterns of the samples, when the dopant concentration increases, the diffraction peaks become broader and the crystallite sizes of nanoparticles decline. Fig. 2 shows the XPS spectrum of the prepared thin-film sample containing 3% iron. The peaks of XPS spectrum with various binding energy are labeled with their associated orbitals. The XPS results confirm the formation of the TiO₂ compound at a surface of thin-film sample and the peaks related to iron can also be distinguished. The carbon peak can be associated with the remaining carbon of organic compounds or absorbed CO₂ at the surface of samples.

Fig. 2. XPS spectrum of TiO₂ : Fe (0.3%) thin-film sample.

The optical absorption spectra of Fe-TiO₂ thin films with different Fe dopant content are shown in Fig. 3. The spectra of pure TiO₂ is assigned to O²⁻ → Ti⁴⁺ charge-transfer and electron excitation from the valance band to the conduction band. The λ_{max} of the Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films with different doping amounts of Fe have a red shift to the visible region and this shift depends on the iron ions content in the lattice. It must be noted that the band gap energy (E_g) of the Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films decrease with an increase in the amount of iron. When the Fe³⁺ ions insert into the lattice, locate at interstices or occupy

Fig. 3. (A) Optical absorption spectra of (a) TiO₂, (b) 0.05% Fe-doped TiO₂, (c) 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂, (d) 1.0% Fe-doped TiO₂ and (e) 3.0% Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films. (B) The maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}).

some of the Ti⁴⁺ lattice sites and the impurity levels appear between the valence band and the conduction band of TiO₂. So decreasing the band gap energy causes the shift of absorption edge to the visible region.

The absorption edge energy (E_g) was obtained through the maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) and reported in Table 1. The 3.0% Fe-TiO₂ thin film expressed the maximum shift, the value of E_g decreasing to 2.95 eV.

The AFM images of Fe-TiO₂ thin films with different Fe dopant content in a scale of 500 $\mu\text{m} \times 500 \mu\text{m}$ are depicted in Fig. 4

The results show a rough surface which is usual for Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films. Images obtained on different regions of thin films showed that the films exhibit a round

structure. According to the statistical data analysis of the AFM images that results are reported in Table 2, it can be found that the surface roughness of the films decrease with the increase in the amount of iron and the average grain size in films increase.

Influence of alcohol on properties of thin films :

The effect of polyalcohol, thin film was synthesized using polyethylene glycol with a similar method. The XRD patterns of 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ power synthesized using polyethylene glycol and 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ powder synthesized using ethylene glycol are shown in Fig. 5.

The 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesized using ethylene glycol possesses the anatase phases while

Table 1. The band gap energy of TiO₂ thin films

Sample	TiO ₂	0.05% Fe-TiO ₂	0.3% Fe-TiO ₂	1.0% Fe-TiO ₂	3.0% Fe-TiO ₂
E_g (eV)	3.21	3.08	3.02	3.00	2.95

Fig. 4. AFM surface topography of (a) TiO₂, (b) 0.05% Fe-doped TiO₂, (c) 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂, (d) 1.0% Fe-doped TiO₂, (e) 3.0% Fe-doped TiO₂ thin films and (f) 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ synthesized using polyethylene glycol.

Surface topographic parameters	Average roughness (nm)	Average grain size (nm)
TiO ₂	2.76	64.5
0.05% Fe-TiO ₂	2.51	72.3
0.3% Fe-TiO ₂	2.35	77
1.0% Fe-TiO ₂	1.96	80.17
3.0% Fe-TiO ₂	1.35	91.92

0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesized using polyethylene glycol is a mixture of anatase and rutile phases and in the XRD patterns appears rutile phases. In XRD patterns of the 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ particles synthesized using polyethylene glycol, the diffraction peaks become broader, and this confirms the decreasing of the crystal-line size.

The AFM images of 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ thin film synthesized using polyethylene glycol in a scale of 500 μm × 500 μm is shown in Fig. 4. The average grain size obtained for the films is around 71.2 nm and the average roughness is 2.5 nm. It can be found that the surface roughness of the film decreases and the average grain size increases with replacement alcohol.

The maximum absorption wavelength of the 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ thin film synthesized using polyethylene glycol (Fig. 6.) was similar to 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ thin film synthesized using ethylene glycol, which indicated that the absorption edge energy of 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ thin film have not changed with using polyethylene glycol.

Photocatalytic test :

The absorbance spectra of methyl orange solution after a photocatalytic test are shown in Fig. 6.

Lower absorbance of solutions related to TiO₂ : Fe (0.3%) sample indicates lower concentration of methyl orange in this solution. Therefore we can conclude that this sample has higher photocatalytic activity in comparison with other samples; even though addition of iron can improve the photocatalytic activity of anatase phase. How-

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of (a) 0.3% Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesized using ethylene glycol and (b) 3.0% Fe-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesized using polyethylene glycol.

Fig. 6. Photocatalytic oxidation of methyl orange on samples (UV-Vis measurements after 5 h light exposure, the legend of each curve indicates the percent of iron).

ever, formation of rutile and brookite phases with lower photocatalytic activity results in lower photocatalytic activity of samples with higher iron concentration. These results indicate that changes of phase content of samples should be considered for studying photocatalytic activity of doped TiO_2 .

Conclusion

The Fe-doped TiO_2 thin films with different Fe dopant content were synthesized by the polymeric precursor method and spin coating. Fe^{3+} ions doped into TiO_2 have caused changes in some properties of the thin films such as crystallite phase, band gap energy, surface roughness and particles sizes. The studies revealed that Fe-doped TiO_2 thin films synthesized using polyethylene glycol and ethylene glycol shown the same maximum absorption and the same absorption edge energy. It can be seen that crystallite phase shows changes with the replacement of the alcohol. The results of photocatalytic test were also showed that the samples with higher anatase phase with little iron concentration have better photocatalytic activity (0.3 mol% of iron).

Acknowledgements

It would be acknowledged that this work was supported by the National Elite Foundation. We are also

grateful to the Institute for Color Science and Technology for their support.

References

1. M. Vishwas, S. K. Sumara, K. Narasimha Rao, S. Mohan, K. V. Arjuna Gowda and R. P. S. Chakradhar, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2010, **75**, 1073.
2. T. Oku, N. Kakuta, K. Kobayashi, A. Suzuki and K. Kikuchi, *Prog. Nat. Sci.*, 2011, **21**, 122.
3. H. L. Wang, D. Y. Zhao and W. F. Jiang, *Desalin. Water Treat.*, 2013, **51**, 2826.
4. N. Pechini, US Patent No. 3, 330, 697, 1967.
5. M. Kakihana, T. Okubo, M. Arima, Y. Nakamura, M. Yashima and M. Yoshimura, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.*, 1998, **12**, 95.
6. D. S. Gouveia, L. E. B. Soledade, C. A. Paskocimas and E. Longo, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2006, **41**, 2049.
7. P. A. Lessing, *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, 1989, **68**, 1002.
8. G. S. Mital and T. Manoj, *Chin. Sci. Bull.*, 2011, **56**, 1639.
9. A. B. Bandgar, S. R. Sabale and S. H. Pawar, *Micro Nano Lett.*, 2011, **6**, 816.
10. R. M. Mohamed, D. L. McKinney and W. M. Sigmund, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, 2012, **73**, 1.
11. K. M. Choi, Y. H. Kim and S. M. Lee, *Desalin. Water Treat.*, 2013, **51**, 3075.
12. Y. Cong, J. Zhang, E. Chen, M. Anpo and D. He, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2007, **111**, 10618.
13. R. S. Sonawane, B. B. Kale and M. K. Dongare, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 2004, **85**, 52.
14. M. C. Wang, H. J. Lin and T. S. Yang, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2009, **473**, 394.
15. F. Sayilkan, M. Asiltuerk, P. Tatar, N. Kiraz, S. Sener, E. Arpac and H. Sayilkan, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2008, **43**, 127.
16. B. R. Sankapal, S. D. Sartale, M. C. Lux-Steiner and A. Ennaoui, *C. R. Chimie*, 2006, **9**, 702.
17. A. Rampaul, I. P. Parkin, S. A. O. Neill, J. Desouza, A. Mills and N. Elliott, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **22**, 35.
18. M. N. Esfahani and M. H. Habibi, *Desalin. Water Treat.*, 2009, **3**, 64.
19. J. Wang, W. Sun, Zh. Zhang, Zh. Jiang, X. Wang, Ru. Xu, R. Li and X. Zhang, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.*, 2008, **320**, 202.
20. S. Bitao, W. Ke, B. Jie, M. Hongmei, T. Yongchun, M. Shixiong, Sh. Shixiong and L. Ziqiang, *Front. Chem. China*, 2007, **2**, 364.
21. K. Naeem and F. Ouyang, *Physica (B)*, 2010, **405**, 221.